

Unique ID	Aliste 2022 DoA	Study ID	Aliste 2022	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique".		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique". <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate."		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.		
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis.		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	Y	Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded.		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	Y			
	Risk of bias judgement	High	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area.		
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN			
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.		
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		

Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Aliste 2022 DoM	Study ID	Aliste 2022	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique".		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique". <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate."		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.		
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis.		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	Y	Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded.		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	Y			
	Risk of bias judgement	High	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as time to first movement of the fingers.		

	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to first movement of the fingers. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Aliste 2022 DoS	Study ID	Aliste 2022	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s): Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique".		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique". <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate."		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1), 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.		
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group were excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1), 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis.		

	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	Y	Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	Y	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as time to normal sensation of the fingers.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to normal sensation of the fingers. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors, the participants, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Aliste 2022 AE	Study ID	Aliste 2022	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s): Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique".		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated sequence of random numbers created by a research assistant and sealed envelope technique". <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> It was not described if trial medication was identical in appearance, volume, etc. However, we assume that trial medication was adequately concealed.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group was excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset.		

	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"All perineural adjuvants were prepared and mixed with the LA by an assistant who was not involved in patient care. Thus, all patients, operators and outcome assessors remained blinded to the nature of the perineural injectate." <input type="checkbox"/> It was not described if trial medication was identical in appearance, volume, etc. However, we assume that trial medication was adequately concealed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/25 participants in the dexamethasone group was excluded from analyses due to block wearing off during sleep (2), inadequate block onset (1), and loss to follow-up (1). 2/25 participants were excluded from the dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine group due to inadequate block onset. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	PN	Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded. This could probably not influence the risk of adverse events substantially.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	No, 6/50 participants were excluded from analysis. <input type="checkbox"/> Participants with inadequate onset of the block and block worn off during night was excluded. This could probably not influence the risk of adverse events substantially. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Various drug-specific adverse events and block-related adverse events were pre-defined on ClinicalTrials.gov and reported.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors were described as unaware of allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Various drug-specific adverse events and block-related adverse events were pre-defined on ClinicalTrials.gov and reported. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors were described as unaware of allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was made available prior to publication. No information on when unblinding was performed. Therefore, not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 DoA	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y	

	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/>
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was performed.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Time to first morphine dose, as recorded by the patient. <input type="checkbox"/>
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Time to first morphine dose, as recorded by the patient. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 DoM	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Duration of motor block	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results."
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was performed.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Time to first movement of forearm/arm.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Time to first morphine dose, as recorded by the patient. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 DoS	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
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Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist	
Outcome	Duration of sensory block	Results		Weight 1	
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.	
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/>	
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		Y		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		PN		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA		
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		Y		Intention to treat analysis was performed.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y		
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA		
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA		
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N	"Time to the patient claims to have started to experience paraesthesia on his/her shoulder after the operation" <input type="checkbox"/>	
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N		
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N		The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA		
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Time to first morphine dose, as recorded by the patient. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.	
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		NI		

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 Pain 24	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1 Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results."		
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was performed.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low			
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Pain at rest at 24 hours measured using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points)		
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N			
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.		
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Pain at rest at 24 hours measured using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 Pain 48	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Pain at 48 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results."		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was performed.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low			

Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Pain at rest at 48 hours measured using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points)
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Pain at rest at 48 hours measured using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 Opioid 24	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results."		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was performed.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>		

Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Cumulative oral morphine intake at 24 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Cumulative oral morphine intake at 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Albrecht 2023 Opioid 48	Study ID	Albrecht 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y		A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist.	
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low		A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to block allocate participants, five to each group. Each allocation was sealed in an opaque envelope, opened on the day of surgery by the participant's anaesthetist. <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N		"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results."	
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	Y			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	PN			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y		Intention to treat analysis was performed.	
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"The control was 100 ml intravenous saline infused over 30 min, containing dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg, after the induction of general anaesthesia. The saline for the intervention group contained dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg, as well as dexamethasone 0.15 mg/kg. We did not blind the anaesthetist to the intervention, which could have systematically biased the results." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Cumulative oral morphine intake at 48 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Cumulative oral morphine intake at 48 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No analysis plan was registered or published.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No analysis plan was registered or published. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome was measured as intended on ClinicalTrials.gov. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns. <input type="checkbox"/>

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 DoA	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?			N	
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study." <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?			N	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags."
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?			N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?			NA	

	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		PN	4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1).
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		PN	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	Almost all participants were analysed.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Almost all participants were analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N	Measured as time to first request of opioids.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N	The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Measured as time to first request of opioids. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		PN	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 Opioid 24	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study." <input type="checkbox"/>		

Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags."
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	PN	4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1).
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	Almost all participants were analysed.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Almost all participants were analysed.
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption. The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 Opioid 48	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response		Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1. Was the allocation sequence random?		Y		"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."
	1.2. Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		

	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study." <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/>
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	PN	4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1).
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	Almost all participants were analysed.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Almost all participants were analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 AE	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags."
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	PN	4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1).
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	Almost all participants were analysed.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Almost all participants were analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PN	Specific treatment-related adverse events were reported.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors were described as blind to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Specific treatment-related adverse events were reported. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors were described as blind to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no description of unblinding.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no description of unblinding. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 Pain 24	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s): Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."	
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study." <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags."	
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA		
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		PN		
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.	
	Risk of bias judgement		High	"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	Almost all participants were analysed.	
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA		
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA		
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Almost all participants were analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N	Measured using the Verbal Rating Scale (0 to 10 points).	
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		PN	The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N		
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA		
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		

Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Chassery 2020 Pain 48	Study ID	Chassery 2020	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response		Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y		"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study."
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		"Using a computer-generated random number table (Stata SE V.11.1 Software), patients were successively assigned randomly to one of the two treatment groups. Allocation numbers were sealed in opaque envelopes and opened successively at the time of inclusion on the day of surgery by a resource not involved in the study." <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N		"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags."
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA		
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		PN		4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1).
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NI		Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement		High		"Patients were blinded to their group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> "The study solutions were prepared by a staff member who was not involved in the study and delivered in unidentifiable bags." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 4/90 participants were excluded due to non-compliance with the analgesia protocol (3) and inclusion by mistake (1). <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y		Almost all participants were analysed.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA		
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		Almost all participants were analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N		Measured using the verbal rating scale (0 to 10 points).
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		PN		
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N		The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation.

	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured using the verbal rating scale (0 to 10 points). <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, i.e. the patients, were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No statistical analysis plan was available. No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No statistical analysis plan was available. No statistical analysis plan was available. There was no information on when unmasking was performed. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Hong 2019 DoA	Study ID	Hong 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap to conceal the allocation, and a researcher allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap to conceal the allocation, and a researcher allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y			
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			

	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Time to first request of analgesia.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Time to first request of analgesia. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	NI	No trial registration.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	No trial registration.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> No trial registration. <input type="checkbox"/> No trial registration.
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 DoA	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome Domain	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1.Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.		
	2.2.Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			

	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Therefore, the analyses was not intention to treat.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	PN	The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 1/30 participants.
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Therefore, the analyses was not intention to treat. <input type="checkbox"/> The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 1/30 participants.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PN	Measured as time to first use of the PCA-device. Data was lost for two participants, one in each group, thereby questioning the validity of this type of measure. However, since data was only lost for one participant in each group, we believed the method was appropriate.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to first use of the PCA-device. Data was lost for two participants, one in each group, thereby questioning the validity of this type of measure. However, since data was only lost for one participant in each group, we believed the method was appropriate. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 DoM	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of motor block	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments

Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	PY	The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described. <input type="checkbox"/> The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PN	Measured as time to "first normal motor function"

	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to "first normal motor function" <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 DoS	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s): Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of sensory block	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described.		

	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		PY	The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described. <input type="checkbox"/> The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		N	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		N	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NI	Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NI	
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		PN	Measured as time to "first normal sensori function"
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Measured as time to "first normal sensori function" <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		PN	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 Pain 24	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			

	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	PY	The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described. <input type="checkbox"/> The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described.
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PN	Measured as most severe pain during the first 24 hours.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as most severe pain during the first 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.

	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 Opioid 24	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response		Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y		Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N		Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA		
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		N		PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		PY		The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.
	Risk of bias judgement		High		Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Furthermore, data was unavailable for an additional 4 participants in each group for the duration of motor block without reasons for missing data described. <input type="checkbox"/> The lost data could probably not substantially impact the results as it was 5/30 participants in each group.

Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Loss to follow-up for 5/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement as reasons for loss to follow-up was not described. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PN	Measured as most severe pain during the first 24 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as most severe pain during the first 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Hong 2021 AE	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			

	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		N	
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		PN	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded.
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, therefore the analyses were no intention to treat. <input type="checkbox"/> The missing data for 2 patients could probably not substantially impact the results.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	Only missing data for 1/30 participants in each group.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Only missing data for 1/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		PY	Only PONV reported.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		NA	
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Only PONV reported. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		NI	No SAP available.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		PN	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	

Unique ID	Hong 2021 Patient satisfaction	Study ID	Hong 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone+dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)

Outcome	Patient satisfaction	Results	Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Patients were randomized 1:1:1:1 to four groups: a Control group, a dexmedetomidine (DMED) group, a dexamethasone (DEXA) group, and a dexmedetomidine plus dexamethasone (DMED-DEXA) group. A computer-generated (www.randomization.com, accessed on 30 May 2019) randomization table with blocks of 4 and 8 was created. The sequence was uploaded into REDCap (redcap.cnuh.co.kr, accessed on 30 May 2019) to conceal the allocation, and a researcher (Y.J.) allocated each patient to the indicated group immediately after patient arrival at the operating room. After preparing the study drugs, the researcher <input type="checkbox"/> exposed to the allocation was not involved in any part of study conduction <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		N	PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Therefore, the analyses were no intention to treat.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		PN	Missing data for 2 patients could probably not impact the results substantially.
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Blinding was described for participants and personnel. Equal volume trial medication was used and prepared by a person not otherwise involved in the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PCA data was lost for 2 patients, one in each group, and these patients were excluded. Therefore, the analyses were no intention to treat. <input type="checkbox"/> Missing data for 2 patients could probably not impact the results substantially.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	Loss to follow-up for 1/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Loss to follow-up for 1/30 participants in each group. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		PN	Measured as time to patient satisfaction on a numerical rating scale of 0 to 10.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N	
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	

	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to patient satisfaction on a numerical rating scale of 0 to 10. <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors, the patients, were described as unaware of treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Kang 2019 DoA	Study ID	Kang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment."		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment."		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." Identical trial medication was described.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." Identical trial medication was described. Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	All participants analysed.		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All participants analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as "time to first rescue analgesic". Rescue analgesic was provided when VAS was >=4/10 despite of patient-controlled intravenous analgesia with fentanyl.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described. <input type="checkbox"/>
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as "time to first rescue analgesic". Rescue analgesic was provided when VAS was >=4/10 despite of patient-controlled intravenous analgesia with fentanyl. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Kang 2019 DoM	Study ID	Kang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of the motor block	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/>		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)		
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			

	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed) <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y		All participants analysed.
	3.2 If N/P/Ni to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA		
	3.3 If N/P/Ni to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA		
	3.4 If Y/PY/Ni to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	All participants analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N		Measured as the time to return of normal grip strength, as judged by the participant.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN		
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N		Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described.
	4.4 If Y/PY/Ni to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA		
	4.5 If Y/PY/Ni to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Measured as the time to return of normal grip strength, as judged by the participant. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI		No SAP available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN		
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN		
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Kang 2019 Opioid 24	Study ID	Kang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s): Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/>		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described.		

	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed) <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	All participants analysed.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All participants analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as cumulative 24 hour morphine equivalents consumption.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as cumulative 24 hour morphine equivalents consumption. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Kang 2019 Pain 24	Study ID	Kang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1. Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/>		
	1.2. Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3. Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			

	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		Y	Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed) <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	All participants analysed.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	All participants analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N	Measured on the Visual Analogue Scale from 0 to 10.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N	Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Measured on the Visual Analogue Scale from 0 to 10. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Blinding of the outcome assessors (i.e. the patient) was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		NI	No SAP available.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		PN	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Kang 2019 AE	Study ID	Kang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments

Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/>
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"We randomly assigned the patients to one of three groups using a computer-generated randomisation tool" <input type="checkbox"/> "Group assignment was conducted using sequentially numbered, sealed opaque envelopes that were opened only after enrolment by one of the authors; this author prepared the study solutions but was not involved in either performing the block procedure or outcome assessment." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed)
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"All enrolled patients, the anaesthesiologist performing the block, and one surgeon (JCY) who performed all the operations were blinded to group allocation." <input type="checkbox"/> Identical trial medication was described. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat was used (all randomised participants were analysed) <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	All participants analysed.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All participants analysed. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	Y	Only specific adverse events were defined and reported (pruritus, sleep disturbance, block-related neurological symptoms, PONV). Unclear if other adverse events were systematically collected.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	NA	
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	Only specific adverse events were defined and reported (pruritus, sleep disturbance, block-related neurological symptoms, PONV). Unclear if other adverse events were systematically collected. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI	No SAP available.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	

	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	No SAP available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 DoA	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Duration of the sensory block	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?			N	No important baseline differences.
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?			N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?			N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?			NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?			NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?			NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?			Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?			NA	
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?			Y	
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?			NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?			NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?			NA	
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?			N	Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area, patient-reported.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?			N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?			N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?			NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?			NA	
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area, patient-reported. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214 .v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214 .v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 DoM	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome Domain	Duration of the motor block	Results		Weight	1
	Signalling question		Response		Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y		Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		No important baseline differences.
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N		The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA		
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		Y		Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low		The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		N		There was some missing data.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		N		
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		PY		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		PY		
	Risk of bias judgement		High		There was some missing data. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N		Measured as time to first movement of the calf muscles.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N		Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N		The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.

	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area, patient-reported. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Pain 24	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	No important baseline differences.		
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 24 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Pain 48	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Pain at 48 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?			N	No important baseline differences.
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1.Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?			N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.
	2.2.Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?			N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?			NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?			NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?			NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?			Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?			NA	

				Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y			
	3.2 If N/P/N/I to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA			
	3.3 If N/P/N to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA			
	3.4 If Y/P/Y/N/I to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA			
	Risk of bias judgement		Low			<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N			Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 48 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N			Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N			The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/P/Y/N/I to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA			
	4.5 If Y/P/Y/N/I to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA			
	Risk of bias judgement		Low			Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 48 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		Y			Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		N			
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		N			
	Risk of bias judgement		Low			Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		Low			

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Pain 72	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Pain at 72 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question		Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?		Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.	
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?		N		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.	
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N		

	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 72 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured at rest using the numerical rating scale (0 to 10 points) at 72 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214 .v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214 .v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Opioid 24	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?			N	No important baseline differences.

	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?		N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?		N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?		NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?		NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?		NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?		Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?		Y	
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?		NA	
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?		NA	
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		N	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 24 hours.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		N	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		N	
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Opioid 48	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome Domain	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
	Signalling question			Response	Comments

Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	No important baseline differences.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 48 hours.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 24 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 Opioid 72	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Cumulative 72 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	No important baseline differences.		
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Intention to treat analysis was used.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 72 hours.		
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.		
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.		
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as the cumulative oral oxycodone consumption at 72 hours. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.		

	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 SAE	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor		
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)			
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist	
Outcome	Serious adverse events	Results		Weight	1	
Domain	Signalling question			Response	Comments	
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?			Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.	
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?			Y		
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?			N		No important baseline differences.
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.	
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?			N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.	
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?			N		
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?			NA		
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?			NA		
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?			NA		
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?			Y		Intention to treat analysis was used.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?			NA		
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?			Y		
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?			NA		
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?			NA		
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?			NA		
	Risk of bias judgement			Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?			N	Assessed using the ICH-GCP definition of serious adverse events.	
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?			N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?			N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.	
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?			NA		
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?			NA		

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Assessed using the ICH-GCP definition of serious adverse events. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Maagaard 2023 AE	Study ID	Maagaard 2023	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Statistical analysis plan (SAP); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record); Personal communication with trialist
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N		No important baseline differences.	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Computer-generated random allocation sequence in blocks of 6 and 9 stratified by site. Concealed in sequentially numbered opaque envelopes that remained closed until a consenting participant was allocated on the day of surgery. The envelopes were only opened by research personnel, who were not otherwise involved in the trial, in charge of preparing the trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> No important baseline differences.		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y		Intention to treat analysis was used.	
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The trial medication was indistinguishable and prepared in two identically appearing syringes. The syringes were marked 'syringe 1' and 'syringe 2', both containing 20ml of transparent trial medication. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Intention to treat analysis was used. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y			
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA			
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA			
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		

Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured using the adverse events definition as outlined in the GCP guidelines.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	Measured and ascertained in the same way.
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The participants were blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured using the adverse events definition as outlined in the GCP guidelines. <input type="checkbox"/> Measured and ascertained in the same way. <input type="checkbox"/> The participants were blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Analysed in accordance with pre-specified plan as registered on https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22491214.v3 prior to unblinded data becoming available. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

Unique ID	Rodrigues 2021 DoA	Study ID	Rodrigues 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Participants were randomized in a 1:1:1 allocation ratio. GraphPad Prism <input type="checkbox"/> version 6.04 for Windows (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA) was used to generate the randomization table in blocks of 20, which was stored on a password-protected spreadsheet by a study staff member not involved in the conduct of the study (L.G.). A separate research associate (F.F.) not involved in the study sequentially obtained blocks of 20 patient assignments, stored them in a locked drawer, and prepared the study interventions.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Participants were randomized in a 1:1:1 allocation ratio. GraphPad Prism <input type="checkbox"/> version 6.04 for Windows (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA) was used to generate the randomization table in blocks of 20, which was stored on a password-protected spreadsheet by a study staff member not involved in the conduct of the study (L.G.). A separate research associate (F.F.) not involved in the study sequentially obtained blocks of 20 patient assignments, stored them in a locked drawer, and prepared the study interventions. <input type="checkbox"/>		

<p>Bias due to deviations from intended interventions</p>	<p>2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?</p>	<p>N</p>	<p>The intervention drugs were diluted in separate 100-mL bags of normal saline. Bag A contained dexmedetomidine or placebo. Bag B was prepared similarly, with dexamethasone or placebo. With these measures we hoped to render the bags indistinguishable to caregivers. The bags were administered in any order starting at the time of ISB performance. Bag A was administered over ten minutes, consistent with the manufacturer's recommendation for dexmedetomidine while bag B was administered over a period of five to ten minutes to avoid perineal discomfort associated with rapid administration of dexamethasone. While anesthesia team members could perceive differences in sedation when dexmedetomidine was used, outcome assessors were not involved in perioperative care, and recovery room nurses were rarely involved in block performance. Thus, we expected to reliably blind at least outcome assessors and patients but did not directly test blinding of the latter.</p>
	<p>2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?</p>	<p>PN</p>	
	<p>2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Analysis followed intention to treat principles.</p>
	<p>2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>Risk of bias judgement</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>The intervention drugs were diluted in separate 100-mL bags of normal saline. Bag A contained dexmedetomidine or placebo. Bag B was prepared similarly, with dexamethasone or placebo. With these measures we hoped to render the bags indistinguishable to caregivers. The bags were administered in any order starting at the time of ISB performance. Bag A was administered over ten minutes, consistent with the manufacturer's recommendation for dexmedetomidine while bag B was administered over a period of five to ten minutes to avoid perineal discomfort associated with rapid administration of dexamethasone. While anesthesia team members could perceive differences in sedation when dexmedetomidine was used, outcome assessors were not involved in perioperative care, and recovery room nurses were rarely involved in block performance. Thus, we expected to reliably blind at least outcome assessors and patients but did not directly test blinding of the latter.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>Bias due to missing outcome data</p>	<p>3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?</p>	<p>Y</p>	
	<p>3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>Risk of bias judgement</p>	<p>Low</p>	
<p>Bias in measurement of the outcome</p>	<p>4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?</p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area.</p>
	<p>4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?</p>	<p>PN</p>	
	<p>4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?</p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Outcome assessors (i.e. the patients) were described as blinded to treatment allocation.</p>
	<p>4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?</p>	<p>NA</p>	
	<p>Risk of bias judgement</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Measured as time to first pain in the surgical area.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Outcome assessors (i.e. the patients) were described as blinded to treatment allocation.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>Bias in selection of the reported result</p>	<p>5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?</p>	<p>NI</p>	<p>The trial was registered prospectively, but there was no description of the planned analyses prior to publication of the trial.</p>

	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	The trial was registered prospectively, but there was no description of the planned analyses prior to publication of the trial. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	Overruled to high due to one or more domains being at some concerns.

Unique ID	Rodrigues 2021 AE	Study ID	Rodrigues 2021	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine	Source	Journal article(s); Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Participants were randomized in a 1:1:1 allocation ratio. GraphPad Prism <input type="checkbox"/> version 6.04 for Windows (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA) was used to generate the randomization table in blocks of 20, which was stored on a password-protected spreadsheet by a study staff member not involved in the conduct of the study (L.G.). A separate research associate (F.F.) not involved in the study sequentially obtained blocks of 20 patient assignments, stored them in a locked drawer, and prepared the study interventions.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Participants were randomized in a 1:1:1 allocation ratio. GraphPad Prism <input type="checkbox"/> version 6.04 for Windows (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA) was used to generate the randomization table in blocks of 20, which was stored on a password-protected spreadsheet by a study staff member not involved in the conduct of the study (L.G.). A separate research associate (F.F.) not involved in the study sequentially obtained blocks of 20 patient assignments, stored them in a locked drawer, and prepared the study interventions. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The intervention drugs were diluted in separate 100-mL bags of normal <input type="checkbox"/> saline. Bag A contained dexmedetomidine or placebo. Bag B was <input type="checkbox"/> prepared similarly, with dexamethasone or placebo. With these measures we hoped to render the bags indistinguishable to caregivers. The bags were administered in any order starting at the time of ISB performance. Bag A was administered over ten minutes, consistent with the manufacturer's recommendation for dexmedetomidine while bag B was administered over a period of five to ten minutes to avoid perineal discomfort associated with rapid administration of dexamethasone. While anesthesia team members could perceive differences in sedation when <input type="checkbox"/> dexmedetomidine was used, outcome assessors were not involved in perioperative care, and recovery room nurses were rarely involved in block performance. Thus, we expected to reliably blind at least outcome assessors and patients but did not directly test blinding of the latter.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	PN			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y		Analysis followed intention to treat principles.	
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NA			

				The intervention drugs were diluted in separate 100-mL bags of normal saline. Bag A contained dexmedetomidine or placebo. Bag B was prepared similarly, with dexamethasone or placebo. With these measures we hoped to render the bags indistinguishable to caregivers. The bags were administered in any order starting at the time of ISB performance. Bag A was administered over ten minutes, consistent with the manufacturer's recommendation for dexmedetomidine while bag B was administered over a period of five to ten minutes to avoid perineal discomfort associated with rapid administration of dexamethasone. While anesthesia team members could perceive differences in sedation when dexmedetomidine was used, outcome assessors were not involved in perioperative care, and recovery room nurses were rarely involved in block performance. Thus, we expected to reliably blind at least outcome assessors and patients but did not directly test blinding of the latter. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	NA		
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	PY		Defined as new persistent neurological symptoms, and adverse events previously related to the interscalene block and unlikely related to dexamethasone/dexmedetomidine. Unclear if adverse events were collected systematically.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN		
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	NA		
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA		
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA		
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Defined as new persistent neurological symptoms, and adverse events previously related to the interscalene block and unlikely related to dexamethasone/dexmedetomidine. Unclear if adverse events were collected systematically. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	NI		The trial was registered prospectively, but there was no description of the planned analyses prior to publication of the trial.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN		
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN		
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	The trial was registered prospectively, but there was no description of the planned analyses prior to publication of the trial. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	

Unique ID	Zhang 2019 DoA	Study ID	Zhang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol; Non-commercial trial registry record (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov record)
Outcome	Duration of analgesia	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated random numbers list" "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this result was not based on intention to treat analyses.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this result was not based on intention to treat analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	No sensitivity analyses were conducted.
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement for duration of analgesia.
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded. <input type="checkbox"/> No sensitivity analyses were conducted. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement for duration of analgesia. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as time to first request of analgesics.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The outcome assessors were described as blinded to allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as time to first request of analgesics. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> The outcome assessors were described as blinded to allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	N	There was no SAP. Duration of analgesia was listed as the primary outcome in the publication, but as a secondary outcome on the trial registration. No pre-defined SAP.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	PN	
	5.3. ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	PN	

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	There was no SAP. Duration of analgesia was listed as the primary outcome in the publication, but as a secondary outcome on the trial registration. No pre-defined SAP. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Zhang 2019 AE	Study ID	Zhang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol
Outcome	Adverse events	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.		
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment." <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group.		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	No sensitivity analyses were conducted.		
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	Y	Participants were excluded due to adverse events.		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	Y			

	Risk of bias judgement		High	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. <input type="checkbox"/> No sensitivity analyses were conducted. <input type="checkbox"/> Participants were excluded due to adverse events. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?		Y	Only nausea/vomiting, blood pressure, heart rate, pruritus, and saturation was mentioned on the trial registration. It is unclear if adverse events were systematically assessed and if so how.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?		NI	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?		NA	
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		NA	
	Risk of bias judgement		High	Only nausea/vomiting, blood pressure, heart rate, pruritus, and saturation was mentioned on the trial registration. It is unclear if adverse events were systematically assessed and if so how. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		N	There was no SAP. Only specific adverse events were mentioned on the trial registration. However, other adverse events were also reported.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?		NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?		NI	
	Risk of bias judgement		Some concerns	There was no SAP. Only specific adverse events were mentioned on the trial registration. However, other adverse events were also reported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement		High	

Unique ID	Zhang 2019 Opioid 48	Study ID	Zhang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol
Outcome	Cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses.		

	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 90 participants were excluded from analyses.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	No sensitivity analyses were conducted.
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 90 participants were excluded from analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> No sensitivity analyses were conducted. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	The outcome was measured as total 48-hour fentanyl consumption based on the patient-controlled analgesia device.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The outcome was measured as total 48-hour fentanyl consumption based on the patient-controlled analgesia device. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	N	There was no SAP.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	There was no SAP. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Zhang 2019 Pain 24	Study ID	Zhang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			

	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment.
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA	
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6. Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses.
	2.7. If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1. Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded.
	3.2. If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	No sensitivity analyses were conducted.
	3.3. If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement
	3.4. If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	High	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded. <input type="checkbox"/> No sensitivity analyses were conducted. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1. Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as pain on the Visual Analogue Scale.
	4.2. Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3. Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4. If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5. If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as pain on the Visual Analogue Scale. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1. Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	N	There was no SAP.
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.

	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	There was no SAP. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	

Unique ID	Zhang 2019 Pain 48	Study ID	Zhang 2019	Assessor	
Ref or Label		Aim	assignment to intervention (the 'intention-to-treat' effect)		
Experimental	Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine	Comparator	Dexamethasone / Dexmedetomidine / Placebo	Source	Journal article(s); Trial protocol
Outcome	Pain at 24 hours	Results		Weight	1
Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments		
Bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld.		
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y			
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N			
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	"Computer-generated random numbers list" <input type="checkbox"/> "The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study" <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers, patients, staff was described as blinded, so we assumed that allocation concealment was upheld. <input type="checkbox"/>		
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment.		
	2.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N			
	2.3. If Y/PY/NI to 2.1 or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the experimental context?	NA			
	2.4. If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA			
	2.5. If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA			
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	N	Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses.		
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.		
	Risk of bias judgement	High	"The randomization table was kept in the hospital pharmacy. The <input type="checkbox"/> study medication and PCIA solutions were prepared by a nurse who did not participate in the study. The patients, surgeon and research staff who enrolled patients and collected study data were blinded to group assignment. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Participants who were randomised were subsequently excluded due to various reasons (re-operation, refused PCIA, haemorrhage, conversion to open surgery, atelectasis, discontinued intervention). Therefore, this was not intention to treat analyses. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement.		
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	N	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded.		
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1: Is there evidence that result was not biased by missing outcome data?	N	No sensitivity analyses were conducted.		
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2: Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement		
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NI			

	Risk of bias judgement	High	5/25 participants were excluded in the dexmedetomidine + dexamethasone group and 4/24 were excluded from the dexamethasone group. A total of 17 out of 97 participants were excluded. <input type="checkbox"/> No sensitivity analyses were conducted. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Measured as pain on the Visual Analogue Scale.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Measured as pain on the Visual Analogue Scale. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome assessors and patients were described as blinded to treatment allocation. <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	N	There was no SAP.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	NI	Not enough information to support a judgement.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	NI	
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	There was no SAP. <input type="checkbox"/> Not enough information to support a judgement. <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall bias	Risk of bias judgement	High	